

AN EXAMINATION OF HUAWEI'S STRATEGIC DECISIONS: BALANCING TENSIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

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Abstract

In this extensive research project, the authors have conducted a comprehensive review and detailed analysis of the business and corporate strategy of Huawei (which is one of the leading firms in the information and communication technology (ICT) sector). The main focus is on understanding how the company navigates strategic tensions. Key areas of the study include the content of Huawei's strategy regarding its vision and mission, the Strategy Process, Strategy Context, and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which are stated in the book "Strategy in an international perspective" that co-authored by Bob de Wit and Ron Meyer.

The report investigates Huawei's approach and policies in making the strategic decision and manage the paradoxes on Profitability vs. Responsibility, Cooperation vs. Competition, Exploration Vs Exploitation and compliance vs. choice to determine how this company has pursued its strategic goals. The research also evaluates the implication of the strategic decisions made by company's strategists regarding innovation, global collaboration, and sustainable business development. Key findings highlight the adaptable response of companies to challenges and their dedication to moral business conduct while contributing to economic growth, technological innovation, and responsible production.

The study also emphasizes the capacity and agility of the company and its top management team to strategically balance short-term profits with long-term sustainability, illustrating its significance in influencing the future of the ICT sector. In fact, the story of Huawei as a successful company has been studied to show the power of accurate strategic decisions in driving financial success aligned with sustainable goals.

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List of Abbreviations

GSPC Global Cyber Security and User Privacy Protection Committee

GDPR General Data Protection Regulation

SAR Specific Absorption Rates

R&D Research and Development

SDG Sustainable Development Goals

PLA People's Liberation Army

ICT Information and Communications Technology

IoT Internet of Things

OS Operating System

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the company Huawei

Huawei is one of the global leaders in the ICT field (information and communications technology), headquartered in Shenzhen and founded in 1987 by Ren Zhengfei, the former officer of People's Liberation Army (PLA). Currently they are employing almost 207,000 employees who work in about 170 regions worldwide, providing products and services to more than three billion people all over the world (Huawei Corporate Information, n.d.). In their vision, they consider themselves obliged to make every person digitally connected no matter where they are and make the world more intelligent.

1.2 Problem Statement

In this research, the focus is on the detailed evaluation of Huawei's organizational and business strategy. The intention is to achieve a detailed understanding of the subject. To carry out this research, it is not enough to only use the information of the company and other sources such as academic sources and reports published by reliable sources have been used so that there is more chance to discover and examine the different layers of the strategy and its implications.

1.3 Research objectives & Research Questions

This research aims to investigate Huawei's strategic decisions in four sections Strategy, Strategy Content, Strategy Process, and Strategy Context which are stated in the book "Strategy in an international perspective" that co-authored by Bob de Wit and Ron Meyer, and focuses on the following two questions:

- What are the key corporate and business strategies of Huawei?
- How does Huawei navigate on the identified tensions within four mentioned sections?

1.4 Introduction to the Report

This report intends to have a detailed review and evaluation of the specified areas of Huawei's business strategy and organizational strategy. These sections (in accordance with the book) are: Strategy, Strategy Content, Strategy Process, and Strategy Context. It has been tried to comprehensively examine the related tensions in each field and identify and evaluate

Huawei's methods for managing paradoxes and making strategic decisions in each sector in order to determine how this company has pursued its strategic goals.

Using a logical path, the framework of this report not only helps in determining and examining the different layers of Huawei's strategy and their reflection in the company's decisions and operation regarding each of the above-mentioned sectors, but also, their consequences and implication in connection with the goals of sustainable development are reviewed and analysed.

Sections 2 to 5 are about tensions in the field of Strategy, Content of strategy, Process of strategy and Context of strategy. Each section addresses the relevant research topics and provides the critical insights based on theories, models and related ideas stated by the book "Strategy in an international perspective" and other insightful literature.

Furthermore, Section 6 will add another layer of analysis by examining how Huawei integrates Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 8, 9, and 12 into its actions connected to the four strategic parts. This reflective evaluation seeks to analyze the success of such inclusion while also giving useful insights into Huawei's commitment to sustainable and ethical business practices.

Finally, this research tries to focus on Huawei's strategic challenges by providing a review and examination based on the theoretical frameworks and personal observations.

2 Literature Review

To answer the research questions and create a theoretical framework, this chapter will critically discuss relevant literature on the research topic presented in the introduction.

2.1 Strategy

In organizational management, strategy, as defined by De Wit (2014), involves understanding internal strengths, weaknesses, external opportunities and threats to guide actions with imagination and judgment. It comprises three dimensions: strategy content (core elements), strategy process (implementation approach) and strategy context (environmental influence). Mintzberg (1987)

Mintzberg (1978) describes strategizing as the process of formulating and implementing strategies to achieve specific goals, involving dealing with strategic problems. De Wit (2014) underscores the importance of aligning strategies with an organizations mission and vision for goal realization and balance.

Mission & Vision

De Wit (2014) underscores the importance of aligning strategies with an organizations mission and vision for goal realization and balance. The identity of an organization should be reflected by their mission. The vision shapes an organizations activities and purpose.

Profitability

To sustain and enhance financial success, it is advisable for companies to consistently monitor and assess their financial performance, pinpoint potential issues and implement required modifications (Margos & Walsh, 2003). Utilizing profitability indicators such as gross profit margin and return on investment is instrumental in gauging financial well-being, enabling businesses to make well-informed choices regarding their operations and strategies (Suardana et al., 2018). Profitability is the extend which a company total income exceeds its total expenses for any given period and is an essential aspect of a company financial performance (Datarails, 2023). Shareholders can benefit from a company's profitability through capital appreciation and dividends (Nism_Admin, 2023).

Shareholders value perspective

According to De Wit (2014) the shareholders' value perspective places a greater emphasis on profitability compared to mere responsibility. In this view, the purpose of businesses is mainly the maximization of the profits for shareholders. Advocates of shareholder perspective argue that a company's success is most effectively measured by the financial performance and the return it provides to its stakeholders (by being financially robust).

Responsibility

Corporate social responsibility had evolved into a crucial element of business activities, placing increasing importance on the ethical and social obligations of corporations. The essence of responsibility revolves around the notions that companies should not only prioritize profit maximization but should also take into account their influence on both society and the environment (Aquilera et al., 2007). As mentioned by De Wit (2004) often, socially responsible behaviour cost money, which can only be partially recouped by the increased social commitment it brings. But If profitability and responsibility are both seen as the ultimate purpose of business firms, the tension becomes even stronger; optimizing the one will be in conflict with the other. Emphasizing profitability means subjecting all investment to an economic rationale. Societally responsible behaviour should only be undertaken if the net present value of such and investment is attractive or there is no legal way of avoiding compliance (De Wit, 2014).

Stakeholder value perspective

According to De Wit (2014), stakeholders are individuals people or even groups who have an interest or a specific 'stake' in the business activities and outcomes of a business. These people can be employees, suppliers but also local communities. The stakeholders value perspective is about creating value for everyone who is involved in the business processes or are impacted by it, not only those who own shares in the company. Stakeholders value perspective is about an organization being good for their employees in a way good working conditions etc. The stakeholders value perspective priorities responsibility above mere profitability.

2.2 Strategy Content

The concept of strategic content encompasses decisions about a company's goals, scope, and competitive strategies (Fahey & Christensen, 1986). Research on strategic content has shown its significant impact on organizational performance, particularly in the public sector (Andrews et al., 2006).

Network level strategy:

A well-structured network level strategy can provide businesses with a competitive advantage by allowing them to leverage the resources and capabilities of their partners, making it difficult for competitors to imitate or replicate their offerings (Coyne & Dye, 1998a). This paper details why there is a major dilemma between the two paradoxes in network level strategy which relates to the topic company, Competitors are the hub of the market relationship and considers as the rivals for the organization because they produce the similar type of product or service. In this paradox the major focus is at either to develop the competitive relationships with other firms or to cooperate with them.(Inayat & Hamid, 2013a).In the study titled Network approaches and strategic management: Exploration opportunities and new trends, it was found that by “Exploring the network approach in strategic management allows one to adopt the category of network strategy, which can be described through the coexistence of cooperation and competition” ([PDF] *Network Approaches and Strategic Management: Exploration Opportunities and New Trends* | Semantic Scholar, n.d.-a) this finding proves that relationship of the tension cooperation vs competition best falls under network level strategy.

cooperation vs competition tension:

Co-operation:

Market size and stage in lifecycle are additional factors to take into account when dealing with the strategic dilemma of cooperation and competition. When markets are in an early phase it has shown to be important for competitors to cooperate aiming at creating a market and a common standard. This fact has been pointed out, for example, in the mobile phone industry.(Kock et al., n.d.-a). Companies develop cooperative relationships with other companies that have indirect competition. Or they create alliances only when there is some superior threat or mutual benefit that can't be achieved lonely (Inayat & Hamid, 2013a) this quote demonstrates the motivation of a company's choice to cooperate. According to (Lendel

et al., 2015a) on cooperation “it is needed that the company understands the goals of its cooperation options and to reflect these into its strategic goals.” Furthermore, the article sets the conditions needed for a successful cooperation strategy. “Managers of a company should consider focusing on establishing a company culture based on communication and collaboration. In addition to the already mentioned recommendations, implementation of which could improve quality of the cooperation environment Use of cooperation strategy in a company is a complex process that requires thorough understanding of the company environment.” (Lendel et al., 2015a) Company managers should be aware that implementation of cooperation strategy also brings certain risks. Otherwise, would this initiative be doomed to failure. In order to succeed in this area, it is a key to identify risk areas early and to take corresponding measures in order to increase probability of success of implementing cooperation strategy in a company(Vodak et al., 2014a). “In the cooperation one should share the operational levels but never share the strategic level’s information. Most importantly employees are the key players of the competitive game so there is a need of continually check there integrity and honesty.”(Inayat & Hamid, 2013a) this quote highlights the importance of the transparency aspect of cooperation. dden purpose is involved in the interest.

competition:

Later on when a market is mature the companies form formal and informal cooperative arrangements. The aim is, of course, to increase the business.(Kock et al., n.d.-a). Competitors never cooperate until there is some mutual benefit or some hidden purpose is involved in the interest. Basically, companies develop cooperative relationships with other companies that have indirect competition. Also details Collaborations are not in the favor of firms in long-run. A highly competitive environment is inevitable for organizations, because such environment will stimulate the organizations for the continuously improvement.(Inayat & Hamid, 2013a) (Akhlaghpour & Lapointe, n.d.-a) further extends this discussion by examining the impact of socially embedded ties on strategic interorganizational system planning, highlighting the potential benefits and drawbacks of such ties.

Embedded Organization Perspective

According to the course literature, managers which hold the embedded organization perspective believe that business is about value creation. They view collaboration as a real alternative and a way of dealing with other competitive organizations. The angle in which this perspective approaches the paradox of competition vs cooperation is as follows:

A firm must not necessarily view the marketplace as a battleground of competition but rather as a medium of cohesive collaboration. The Embedded Organization type of perspective requires a manager who is hands on and always updating and updated in unison on current affairs within the partnership. Furthermore, firms that hold this perspective believe that more can be achieved this way rather than competing. The main way this works is by a firm recognizing that by using collaboration they will be able to achieve a common or even greater objective. Finally, a firm needs to specialize in a specific area so as to gain scale and experience advantages then they can use their resources and collaborative agreements with their partners in their industry to create a new product or service. A benefit of the embedded organization perspective is that firms can be increasingly integrated into webs of mutually dependent organizations. The inherited challenge with this perspective is that a firm needs to be sure as much as possible that their partners will not behave opportunistically and are also willing to invest in the relationship (Wit, 2020).

2.3 Strategy Process

The process of developing, utilizing and modifying strategies is influenced by the strategy process itself. It involves an approach, to addressing questions about who, what and when strategies are established. Scholars like Wit (2020) emphasize the importance of understanding the duration and steps involved in creating, evaluating, implementing and managing strategies. Additionally it is crucial to identify the stakeholder groups involved in these processes. This detailed summary forms a basis for exploring the nuances and complexities of planning procedures. Van De Ven (1992) highlights the significance for scholars to establish and clarify the theory and meaning underlying the strategy process. This call for clarification suggests that comprehending the participants and states involved in these operations is essential for advancing this field of study. Mintzberg and Quinn (1992) contribute to this discourse by providing an overview of processes. Their research delves into concepts and perspectives related to development offering insights, into its inherent nature.

Strategic Innovation

Schlegelmilch et al. (2003) describe innovation as a reassessment of business models and transformations within markets. Kataria (2013) identifies learning processes, top management teams and entrepreneurial leadership as key factors driving strategic innovation. Intentional learning promotes adaptability, which's essential for innovation. Diverse teams contribute perspectives that enhance decision making while entrepreneurial leaders foster a culture. Anderson and Markides (2006) emphasize that organizations displaying cutting edge tactics, against competitors demonstrate innovation highlighting its nature.

Furthermore, Snyder and Duarte (2003) emphasize the significance of embedding innovation as a capability, throughout the organization. This highlights the commitment needed for innovation. Strategic innovation thrives on learning, diverse leadership and an entrepreneurial mindset. Gaining an advantage relies on adopting tactics while integrating innovation holistically across all aspects of the company is vital (Kataria, 2013; Anderson & Markides 2006; Snyder & Duarte 2003). This concise literature review underscores the nature of innovation by highlighting its various drivers and overall impact on organizations.

Exploitation Vs Exploration Paradox:

Exploitation

The continuous process of improving goods and services to enhance a business capacity is referred to as renewal or exploitation. It involves a pursuit of quality standards increased productivity and consistently enhancing value propositions for marketing, sales and after sales in a more cost effective manner. Each time higher quality is achieved it sets a benchmark (Wit, 2020). From an innovation perspective Piruncharoen et al. (2011) argue that businesses should evaluate their exploitation strategy considering factors such, as compatibility and cost. The importance of adopting an flexible approach, to business exploitation is highlighted by the findings of these research efforts.

Exploration:

The concept of innovation or exploration refers to a process where new technologies and business models are introduced to challenge established competitive positions. To navigate

this landscape successfully strategists must use their creativity to discover inventions that have the potential to revolutionize their industries. Contrary to the belief that disruptive inventions are solely driven by facts they are actually actively created than derived (Wit, 2020). This emphasis on thinking underscores the nature of disruptive innovations.

In the field of business strategy within the context of family businesses choosing an exploration strategy is a decision influenced by various factors such as ambition, aversion to risk and long term orientation (Ibrahim et al., 2019). The significance of this decision is more pronounced in sectors like oil and gas where exploration strategies play a role. Important considerations in this context include having an objective, an established cost structure and a high probability of success (Kolundžić, 1996). As Quick (1982) suggests, it is vital to establish a connection, between exploration strategies, long term goals and corporate strategic planning. A defined exploration plan requires objectives and alignment, with the company's overall goals. Ginevičius and Korsakiene (2005) emphasize the significance of a strategy that connects to a business's goals, capabilities and competitive advantage. This alignment ensures that the exploration strategy not only serves as a means to achieve long term objectives but also integrates smoothly with the organization's strategic planning.

Strategic Improvement Perspective:

Supporters of the improvement perspective argue that businesses should focus on enhancing their business models. The starting point is recognizing the competition among businesses vying for the customer base. To attain success it is crucial to offer value propositions that are both affordable and innovative since customers have various options for meeting their needs. By offering products and services companies can attract customers, expand their market share and generate higher profits (Wit, 2020).

Radical Rejuvenation Perspective:

According to proponents of the radical rejuvenation perspective, companies should focus on breakthrough innovations that change the rules of the competitive game rather than becoming better at playing by the current rules. Game-changing innovations provide innovators with a significant competitive advantage, forcing rivals to follow and play by their rules. (Wit, 2020)

2.4 Strategy Context

Every strategy, no matter how well thought out or implemented, will behave differently in various contexts (De Wit, 2020). Mintzberg (1992) and Wit (1994) give special attentions to the significance of the context in strategic decision making, with Mintzberg differentiating between various organizational settings and Wit highlighting industrial, organizational, and international contexts. Coltman (2005) and Owens (2007) dive more into the links between strategy and performance, Coltman focussing on electronic business performance and Owens exploring strategic thinking. McCabe (2000) and Eden (1993) rather look at very practical examples of strategy, with McCabe providing a framework for simulation and Eden makes use of a case study to practically demonstrate strategy creation and strategic control. Finally, Steen (2018) further broadens the field of strategy by including competitive interactions and emphasizing the strategic value of quantity-based action.

Industry Context

In terms of the industry context, the focus is set on how the industry of the particular company is developing and how a company can influence or be influenced by its industry context (De Wit, 2020). A variety of studies have stressed the emphasis of being able to identify the industry environment in strategy development. Diderich (2019) and Wit (1994) both emphasize the need to consider the industrial environment, with Diderich giving the focus to the views of consumers, industry, firms and external limitations. Slevin (1997) and Lei (2005) delve deeper into the impact of industry context on strategy, with Slevin discovering that different strategies are more effective in different organizational and environmental contexts, and Lei claims a new a typology of industry environments and their strategic imperatives. Together the studies highlight the importance and significance of the industrial environment in making valid strategic choices.

Compliance vs Choice

The decision between compliance and strategic innovation in industries is difficult and impacted by a variety of circumstances. Brockhoff (1999) and Rossi (2010) both emphasizes the many tactics used by businesses to address environmental problems, with the latter highlighting the necessity of self-regulation as a key business competence. Butler (1986) and

Geiger (1998) emphasize the importance of a strategic fit between a firm's strategy and the regulatory environment, with the former proposing a model that considers task ambiguity and concentration, and the latter investigating the impact of the regulatory environment on firm performance. Subramanian (2007) and Bayer (2006) look at the particular contexts of emissions permits and tax compliance, with the former highlighting trade-offs in compliance techniques and the latter investigating the influence of audit procedures on tax compliance. Finally, Bergquist (2012) presents a case study of the Swedish industrial sector, emphasizing the importance of performance criterias in promoting environmental compliance and innovation.

Perspectives on the Tension

Understanding the relationship, between industry dynamics and industry leadership perspectives can be complex as both factors play roles in shaping a companys strategy. According to the author Carpenter (2009) industrys dynamics refers to influences that impact a companys position while Life (1986) defines industry leadership as the CEOs personality, motivation and ability to drive strategic change inside a company. Abell (2006) emphasizes the importance of leadership in aligning a companys vision, goals, resources and market prospects to gain an advantage. In their works Mubarak (2019) and Safarzadeh (2015) highlight the impact of leadership on strategy execution and overall organizational success in gaining a competitive advantages. Additionally Grimm (2005) and Ireland (2013) offer frameworks for leveragings industry dynamics and strategic input to establish a enduring advantage, over competitors.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

3 Methodology

The following chapter deals with the methods used for conducting this research project. Also, it provides an overview of the procedures and data collection methods that were used to collect and analyze information on Huawei's strategy.

3.1 Research Approach

The qualitative approach is employed to analyze sources in order to understand the evolution of the organization, technological advancements and market strategies.

3.2 Data Collection

The data collection process, for this study involved gathering information from a variety of sources including journals, industry reports, official publications, financial records and reputable online databases. We specifically chose these sources because they offer insights into Huawei. Our primary focus was on maintaining accuracy standards by relying on peer reviewed research published in journals.

To ensure that our data collection process was relevant to our research topics related to Huawei publications and literature we conducted searches using keywords such as "innovation," "technology," "market analysis " and "Huawei." Our inclusion criteria prioritized both the credibility of the sources and their relevance, to our research topics.

3.3 Data Analysing,

To effectively analyze the data we collected we utilized a method that focused on identifying recurring themes and patterns. Our main goal was to gain insights by exploring themes related to Huawei's innovations, market position and strategic initiatives. We chose this analysis method because thematic analysis offers a framework, for organizing and interpreting data. This approach enables us to spot trends that contribute to our understanding of Huawei's business strategies and their broader implications, in the technology sector.

3.4 Reliability

To ensure the reliability of this research we have utilized sources known for their trustworthiness and impartiality. We have incorporated publications and scholarly journals to strengthen the accuracy of our gathered data. Additionally we conducted peer debriefing, where all researchers thoroughly examined and endorsed the analysis process, data interpretation as the identified themes and factors. This important step ensures consistency in how different observers comprehend the data thereby enhancing the dependability of our methodology.

3.5 Validity

In terms of validity we ensured the accuracy of our research by evaluating whether the sources we selected effectively address our research questions. By considering perspectives from both industry experts and academic sources, in our study findings we have improved the credibility of our conclusions.

3.6 Ethical considerations:

Ethical considerations are acknowledged in this study. we recognize the importance of respecting intellectual property rights and maintaining confidentiality. It emphasizes our commitment to refrain from using or disclosing information during the process of data collection and analysis in order to uphold standard.

3.7 Limitations,

While we have taken steps to ensure the robustness of this study it is important to acknowledge its limitations. Firstly our reliance, on information may limit our access to confidential data, which could impact the comprehensiveness of our analysis. Secondly considering the evolving nature of the technology sector and market conditions there is a possibility that some of the data used in this study may become outdated over time potentially affecting its relevance. Additionally it should be noted that biases inherent, in the selected sources could influence our findings. Lastly focusing solely on Huawei may not provide a picture of advancements and market dynamics as a whole, which poses a limitation in terms of scope.

4 Description of Huawei's Business strategies

Huawei's business strategy revolves around technology development. It has consistently made investments, in research and development to foster innovation in fields, like cloud computing, artificial intelligence and 5G technologies. Huawei has also formed partnerships with businesses to navigate various legislative frameworks and cultural contexts.

In addition to its core telecom infrastructure sector Huawei has diversified its offerings to include consumer electronics like wearables, tablets and smartphones. This diversification allows Huawei to access a range of markets and reduces dependence on any product area. Furthermore Huawei places importance on building an ecosystem of products and services by fostering collaboration between its software and hardware divisions. This integration aims to enhance user experience by providing connectivity between devices, networks and services.

Despite achieving success Huawei has faced challenges primarily in the arena. Concerns related to trade tensions and security have compelled the company to adapt its approach and explore opportunities, for growth.

In summary Huawei's current approach, to business is expected to focus on advancements expanding globally diversifying its offerings integrating with ecosystems and adjusting to geopolitical challenges.

5 Tension 1

5.1 Identification and description of Huawei's position on the tension

Profitability Vs Responsibility

Radiation of devices from Huawei case

Bases on a study of McCarthy (2018) about which smartphone emits the most radiation, the Huawei Mate 9 is ranked in the top three for emitting the most radiation in 2018 (as visible in graph 1 radiation overview). Most of the devices with elevated radiation levels come from Chinese brands, including Xiaomi, Huawei, OnePlus and ZTE, with 10 out of the top 16 smartphones. (McCarthy, 2019).

Huawei ensures affordability of its phone through innovation and efficient production, making them assessable to diverse consumers. However, a debate within the scientific community revolves around potential radiation effects from Huawei phones. While there is no consensus on the impact of mobile phone radiation, studies highlight potential risks of radiation such as stress and sleep problems (Thomee et al., 2011). Concerns exist regarding the radiation of Huawei's phone on humans' health (Mahila, 2021; Smitha & Narayanan, 2015). Reported risks related to mobile phone use, such as accidents and chronic disorders, also include those associated with Huawei phones.

Figure 1 Radiation overview (McCarthy, 2019)

Creating phones with lower Specific Absorption Rates (SAR) to protect users from radiation might increase production cost by requiring additional design elements or materials (Department of Health & Human Services, n.d.). The inclusion of materials or components to minimize radiation exposure, such as shielding materials or hand-free kits, could further raise the phone's cost (Health Risk From Mobile Phone Radiation – Why the Experts Disagree, n.d.). Moreover, investing in research and development to reduce radiation levels in phones may demand extra resources and funding, potentially impacting the overall product costs. Taking into account of less radiation, will lead to more expensive phones which can result in selling less phones to customers with a lower budget of money to spend.

5.2 Evaluation of the position taken by Huawei

Huawei focus on affordable smartphones through innovation raised concerns about potential radiation effects. Huawei's strategy was about producing phones affordability and making the phone assessable to diverse consumers. Because the phones of Huawei are affordable, the study of McCarthy (2019) has highlights the big amount of radiation the phones spread, which can be considered as bad for human's health. Because the strategy of Huawei was about selling affordable phones, Huawei could not take in to account of extra cost for less radiation on their devices.

This suggest that Huawei possible prioritizes profitability over addressing potential health risk associated with their devices. Huawei chooses profitability above responsibility.

Shareholders value perspective

The most suitable perspective related to the radiation case of Huawei, seems to be the shareholders' value perspective. According to De Wit (2014) does this perspective contends that a company's primary responsibility is to deliver value to its shareholders through robust financial performance.

Do I agree with the position taken by Huawei on the tension?

No, I do not agree with the taken position by the company. As the literature review highlighted, the radiation what the Huawei Mate 9 emits, is really bad for consumers and also employees who have to produce that devices health. The health risk related to the radiation.

is according to Thomee et al. (2011) so bad for humans' health that they lead to potential risks such as stress and sleep problems. Of course, I do understand that company's wanting to make as much as profit as possible but If I where Huawei, I would not like and want to be responsible for health problems which are related to the products that I am selling to them.

Management of the paradox

The tension for Huawei is about being responsible and taking into account of the health of their consumers or about making more profit/ ROI. This paradox should be managed by balancing. According to De Wit (2014) does balancing means, a bit of both. So, for Huawei does that mean that the company should take in to account of the amount radiation their devices can have. They need to take in to account of their customers health and decrease the health risks associated with their phones. On the other hand, they still want and need to make profit. By the balancing approach they have to make a bit more cost on spending money on their production for their devices, for example when Huawei invest in research and development to reduce radiation levels in phones, the radiation level om the Huawei 9 could be decreased after knowing by research and development how to handle. On the other hand, the production price needs to be a bit higher than before.

5.3 Reflections on performance and advice related to SDG – 9, 8 and 12

Reflection on SDG'S 8,9 and 12

SDG 8 Focussing on decent work and economic growth

- **Positive aspects:** Huawei's focus on mass production and innovation in the smartphone sector contributes to job creation in the technology industry. This aligns with SDG 8's goal of promoting a overall sustainable economic growth, as well as full and productive employment possibilities. The focus on innovation within the smartphone production-sector demonstrates a high commitment of Huawei to advancing technology and staying competitive in their market. This contributes indirectly but positively to economic growth and job creating aligning with SDG 8's objectives.

- **Challenges:** The study by McCharty (2019) raises concerns about radiation in Huawei phones, which can potentially impact the well-being of employees and consumers. These risks imply a contradiction to the aspect of working condition as mentioned in the SDG 8 because not only the health and safety of people that are involved in the production but also the end users of these phones are potentially being put in danger.

SDG 9 Focussing on industry, innovation and infrastructure

- **Positive aspects:** Huawei's goal of innovating on smartphones aligns with SDG 9's focus on industry, innovation and infrastructure. These efforts directly contribute to the technological advancements in their industry.
- **Challenges:** The potential health risks associated with radiation from Huawei's phones may raise concerns about the long-term sustainability of company. This indicates a challenge to the goal of SDG 9, because being sustainable and durable as a company is a key element in ensuring the long-term success in industry and innovation.

SDG 12 Focussing on responsible consumption and production

- **Positive aspects:** Since this case is about the product Huawei Mate 9 and this device in the top 3 of emitting the most radiation belongs, is there no positive aspect about consuming and producing responsibly.
- **Challenges:** The study by McCharty (2019) indicates that Huawei's Mate 9 smartphones may not be produced responsibly due to the radiation concerns. This suggests that Huawei may prioritize profit over responsible production practices, presenting a challenge to SDG 12, which focusses on promoting responsible consumption and production. (THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development, n.d.)

6 Tension 2

6.1 Identification and description of Huawei's position on the tension

Huawei was fighting for its survival four years ago, in 2020 Huawei fell out of the global top 5 smartphone manufacturing companies as a result of the intensive trade war and economic sanctions that were placed on the company. In the international markets there was the Google ban which banned Huawei from being able to gain access to the Google play store and other google services like for example Gmail, Google maps, Google docs to name a few. The google ban did not have a significant effect inside China domestic market however the single most devastating blow came to Huawei as a company was the denial of access to critical microchip processors it needs to power their product. This denial to critical hardware caused Huawei to fall below their domestic competition companies like: Xiaomi, Oppo, Apple, and Vivo. Because of that Huawei slowly was running out of microchips and also running out of products it could deliver to consumers. Huawei and its more than 200,000 employees needed to make a transformation quickly. When you fast forward to today it is back on track with its \$100 billion-dollar revenue furthermore according to (Nyame, 2023a)“the conglomerate, based in Shenzhen, shared on Friday that it anticipates generating over 700 billion yuan (\$99 billion) in revenue in 2023. This reflects a 9% increase from the 642.3 billion yuan (\$92.4 billion) recorded in 2022”. This rebound effect can also be observed in their current standing of smartphone manufacturers “Huawei is the sixth largest Smartphone manufacturer company in the world with was 4% smartphone market share in July 2023”(Elad, 2023a). How did Huawei be able to have such a successful rebound? one aspect will be the strategic shift Huawei had to make from being a company that sells hardware to a company which sells software.

6.2 Evaluation of the position taken by Huawei

At its core Huawei has a strong emphasis on research and development of their products. Harmony OS is the result of that research and development. When HarmonyOS was initially announced in 2019 the company marketed it as an in house developed alternative to android operating system. With time however it formed into a hybrid distributing operating system. As detailed in the article (Sheng Weng, 2020a)HarmonyOS is an open a unified Operating System. This means that it is designed to work on various type of hardware not just

smartphones but also tablets, smart TVs, smart watches, in car infotainment systems, IoT Devices, smart oven, smart fridges. This software allows all of these devices for pair and share data seamlessly regardless of the other devices operating system, for example applications developed using the HarmonyOS can run on a Huawei smartphone that runs android, a Huawei smartwatch that runs LiteOS smartwatches, Huawei in car infotainment system simultaneously. This cross compatibility is was described in the article by (Sheng Weng, 2020a) “Its creation was originally designed for industrial and telecommunications networks, not as you think it is designed for mobile phone operating systems used in mobile phones, when doing this system does not want to replace Android.” Another way this can be observed is when a customer uses a HarmonyOS application on their phone, it will run smoothly like a regular app, that same application can also run on the Smartwatch in the form of a smartwatch app, and can also run on the tv as a tv application.

This platform allows for greater cooperation between Huawei and app developers in the sense that the app developers need to only work with one code for app development through Harmony OS this app will be able to be then compatible on multiple devices automatically rather than the developer separately write a specific code for each device. Huawei has essentially created a platform that is integrates with all their various devices under one umbrella system which is the HarmonyOS. Also, Huawei’s main cooperation strategy can be seen by looking at their local competitors. All of the Chinese phone manufacturers have started to diversify their own product portfolios offering more smart connected devices, the problem they faced is that each of those products are made by third party contract manufacturers and because of that they are facing connectivity problems between all their devices. Google is not present in China which means that there is a fragmented phone manufacturing ecosystem. All their smartphone companies must create their own Appstore, their own bundle of apps etc. with Harmony OS it can become the cross company and cross device platform for the whole Chinese phone market. Also, Chinese smartphones manufacturers has seen the detrimental effect the sanctions have had on Huawei and very much looking to strengthen domestic platforms wherever possible so that they are ale to avoid the same fate occurring to them as well. This is a compelling factor for this case. The CEO of Huawei Ren Zhengfei stated that “A closed culture cannot absorb the strengths of others and will gradually be marginalized. A closed organization will eventually become like

stagnant water. We must openly learn from others in every area, such as R&D, sales, services, supply management, and financial management.

“We must not cling to what has worked in the past and become self-centered. In our process of innovation, we need to stand on the shoulders of giants and absorb as many external strengths as possible in the same way as a sponge absorbs water. We must not pursue independent innovation behind closed doors. With openness, Huawei will be able to survive in the long run. Without openness, it will soon perish.” (Ren Zhengfei: Deepening Our Understanding of the Corporate Culture of Staying Customer-centric and Inspiring Dedication, 2008) (Huang, 2019a). There is a clear shift from simply being a hardware manufacturing company competing with Apple and Samsung in a market where almost all the products used there are made to run under their competitors OS. To being a cooperative domestic software development giant that can encompass all the Chinese phone companies as China’s answer to the wests operating software ecosystems.

Embedded Organization Perspective according to Huawei

However, as we all cannot read each other’s minds and cannot fully know each other’s intentions. There are some strategic ways this can be mitigated or managed. I think Huawei applies this perspective because firstly, a firm must develop a strong trust in their relationship with their partners also there needs to be measures of transparent communication between the partners so as to clarify any doubts that can arise in the process of collaboration also, any concerns can be discussed and addressed thoroughly at this time. The reason this is done is to maintain the alignment of objectives and goals wherein they continue to remain parallel with each other. According to the quote “In order to succeed in this area, it is a key to identify risk areas early and to take corresponding measures in order to increase probability of success of implementing cooperation strategy in a company” by the Scholar (Vodak et al., 2014a) Huawei can enable the trust of the other firms in the industry to use this by offering them a full turnkey solution package for the domestic phone market. An Embedded Organization has measures in place to support that a firm must have a strong conflict resolution measure must be in place in the event of any misunderstanding or dispute can be resolved in an effective and professional manner. This is also in relation to was discussed by (Lendel et al., 2015a) when they said “Managers of a company should consider focusing on establishing a company culture

based on communication and collaboration". The transparent flow of information between partners shows that a firm must reciprocate in order to continue the collaboration and as when (Inayat & Hamid, 2013a) revealed "Most importantly employees are the key players of the competitive game so there is a need of continually check there integrity and honesty." hey. That is what Huawei is doing by simply allowing the platform to be open-source that means that anybody has access to improve and work on further innovation and development of Harmony OS.

Do I agree with the position taken by Huawei on the tension?

I agree with the position Huawei took regarding the Tension of Cooperation vs Competition in moving more to the Cooperation side of the paradox as considering the volatile situation they faced, Huawei had to decide fast, and ultimately, they made the right choice. The decision Huawei took is also more in line with a long-term strategy rather than a short-term strategy. Huawei is correct in choosing to cooperate rather than to compete presently, as by seeking to cooperate domestically with the other phone manufacturers in China they can become the domestic market leader in the operating systems space which will facilitate them to make a new shift in the future by competing with the other international companies like Samsung and Apple against their operating systems. This is further proven by the most recent data "HarmonyOS was deployed on 330 million Huawei devices and used in 12 different types such as smartphones, PCs, Huawei Vision products, tablets, smartwatches, earphones, and head units for enabling enhanced interaction" (Elad, 2023a). This is a rational decision in my view because in the way that their competitors allow other phone manufacturers to use their operating systems, they have become key players in their respective markets. The question is why can't Huawei do the same?

Managing of the paradox

Huawei can use " Navigating" as a way to solve the paradox of Competition vs Cooperation by navigating the paradox Huawei can change their strategy when the time is right for example Huawei's Strategy was competition in the past, the strategy now in this present time is cooperation, In the future once Huawei has the leverage to do so they can move to competing again. It is also forcing Huawei to focus on one contrary element at a time thus allowing them to gain a clearer view on which position to shift to in the future. "Navigating" is also recognized

as the least complex of the other two management forms. “Parallel processing” is more related to a different industry than what Huawei is involved in. Finally, in “juxtaposing” while theoretically possible is much harder in real time practice to compete one hundred percent whilst simultaneously cooperate this is where the concept of cooptation comes from.

6.3 Reflections on performance and advice related to SDG – 9, 8 and 12

SDG 8: Focus on decent work and economic growth

- **Job Creation:** The way Harmony OS contributes to economic growth is by creating more Jobs, Huawei allows for developers, manufacturers, and services providers to openly collaborate with each other in order to further develop and expand the Harmony OS ecosystem. Harmony OS is designed to encompass a wide range of devices. This drastically reduces the workload of app developers.
- **Digital Skills Development:** Huawei can be able to initiate partnership programs with institutions as well as offer inhouse training programs to help build the necessary digital development skills among individuals and other businesses to navigate the Harmony OS platform. This contributes to SDG 8 directly as it promotes a skilled workforce and enhances employability. These skilled subject matter experts in Harmony OS can then not only work for Huawei but also work in the domestic Chinese phone market.
- **Inclusive Economic growth:** Harmony OS could possibly be designed with simplicity in mind in order to reach a broader userbase making it more accessible to users who are within developing regions in the world market. By having this inclusivity Huawei fosters economic growth by ensuring the benefits of technologic enhancements can be shared among different demographic groups. Harmony OS also included the other mobile phones manufacturers who will be using the platform in the domestic market to boost domestic cooperation.

SDG 9: Focus on industry innovation and infrastructure

- **Connectivity and Accessibility:** Harmony OS is designed to provide seamless connectivity between all its devices this means that it provides a connected ecosystem. The integration with IoT devices (internet of things) like smart home appliances and infotainment systems this further enhances connectivity and interoperability. by including Harmony OS Connect a feature that allows even third-party devices that don't have Harmony OS to be able to connect to the Harmony OS ecosystem. This ties into SDG 9 by promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization, continuous improvement in innovation, and enhancing technologic infrastructure for all.
- **Technological Innovation:** The contribution to research and development of new solutions Huawei has committed itself to innovation by developing Harmony OS platform. By coniously investing in this platform Huawei is further accelerating the speed at which technological innovation occurs. It contributes directly with SDG 9 by promoting sustainable technologies and innovation. Harmony OS is a unique approach to the concept of an operating system that was to attempted by another company before them.
- **Cyber security measures:** Harmony OS will operate under a rigid cybersecurity framework. A few examples of what Harmony OS offers includes; constant security updates, security polies this allows users and developers to set security policies and enforce restrictions and remotely manage security settings , firewall and intrusion detection, encryption, safe application security measures so as to not have apps which are malicious or have viruses, secure boot processes this will make sure that only authenticated and authorized code is executed during system startups. This is why it contributes to the sustainable developments of digital networks and infrastructure.

SDG12: Focus on responsible consumption and production

- **Extended Product Lifecycles:** By providing regular software updates and support for older devices Huawei can contribute to reducing electronic waste, and promote responsible consumption. Also, by extending the product lifecycle Huawei are supporting the customer in turn because they are producing a well-rounded high-quality product.
- **Efficient Resource Use:** Huawei can in the future optimize Harmony OS to be more resource efficient from minimizing the environmental impact associated with excessive resource consumption such as its effect on CPU, memory, and how it affects product battery life.

The reason that this case relates to Network Level Strategy and not Business Level nor is it Corporate Level strategy is because, Huawei is as a company seeks to use Harmony OS to solve the Network Level issue of interfirm relations. Huawei seeks to build its relations within the Chinese domestic network of phone manufacturing companies therefore in return of developing this network Huawei itself as accompany can grow. Corporate level strategy mostly deals with the issues related to corporate configuration of a company, for example deciding what organization system is required to run a firm or in what lines of a business should a corporation be active. Business level strategy pertains to how exactly can a firm use its own resources within the company to handle the issue of competitive advantage. These resources are a firms primary activities for example logistics or marketing and sales and a firms secondary activities HRM or procurement. It deals mostly with the either the creating value for the customer or market adaptations.

7 Tension 3

7.1 Identification and description of Huawei's position on the tension

Exploration Vs Exploitation

Exploration Strategy:

As a part of their strategy Huawei has developed its app ecosystem called App Gallery in response, to the Google Play Store. This move highlights Huawei's aim to build their ecosystem and decrease dependency on existing platforms. The impressive progress made by Huawei can be credited to their approach. Unwavering determination, in overcoming challenges.

Evidence of Exploration: In August 9 2019 Huawei unveiled Harmony OS, their operating system that aims to drive innovation. In order to address the challenges posed by the ban, on accessing US based technologies Huawei made the decision to embrace technologies and explore alternative business models. As a result they developed their operating system known as "HarmonyOS."

Creative Thinking and Breaking Rules: HarmonyOS represents a departure, from the approach showcasing Huawei's problem solving skills and open mindedness. The bold move aimed to safeguard the company's future and reduce dependence on factors. By introducing an alternative to Android Huawei sought to ensure the operation of their business ventures. This strategic exploration extended to the launch of the Mate 30 series (as explained by Huawei in 2023) which notably did not include Google apps. Despite facing challenges along the way the Mate 30 series managed to achieve its objectives thanks in part to unwavering support, from the Chinese market.

Innovator's Paradox: The ban has forced a situation arose wherein they had to navigate the complexity of implementing new technologies, such as HarmonyOS. Specifically, quantifying the potential of their existing capabilities, such as the App Gallery. This challenge is frequently referred to as the paradigm of innovation.

Exploitation Strategy:

In the year 2020 Huawei made a decision to sell off its subbrand, HONOR. This move allowed the company to concentrate its resources and mitigate the impacts of the ban, on one of its

divisions. It's worth noting that Huawei adeptly navigated the challenges posed by the ban by finding an equilibrium, between seizing opportunities and forging paths. The company successfully maintained a balance by being mindful of risks while staying focused on its core strengths.

Evidence of Exploitation: After realizing the importance of expanding its business operations beyond China Huawei chose to adopt a growth oriented strategy. The company dedicated itself to improving its offerings with an emphasis, on strengthening its operations.

Customer Feedback and Market Research: Huawei took customer feedback and market demands into account when making adjustments, in accordance with their improvement principles. A noteworthy example of this is their effort to develop a substitute for the Google Play Store by utilizing their existing capabilities (The HUAWEI Ban Explained, 2023). Huawei intends to enhance and refine its product portfolio leveraging its established position, in the market.

Risk of Falling Behind: The ban, on Huawei has forced the company to seek alternatives and adapt in order to stay competitive in the smartphone market. Without these adjustments Huawei might have fallen behind its rivals. Essentially Huawei now finds itself in a position where it needs to explore strategies and leverage its strengths. The ban has pushed the company to utilize its existing advantages identify growth opportunities and take calculated risks to overcome challenges. The way Huawei effectively manages this balancing act will greatly affect its long term sustainability, in the smartphone industry.

7.2 Evaluation of the position taken by Huawei.

When analyzing Huawei's position during the tension and the subsequent ban it is important to take into account a range of factors. These include evaluating the company's responses, strategies, challenges encountered and the resulting outcomes. Assessing Huawei's position from perspectives is crucial, in understanding their situation:

Radical Rejuvenation Perspective (Exploration Strategy): The sale of its sub-brand HONOR (The HUAWEI Ban Explained, 2023) and the launch of Harmony OS, across products

demonstrates Huawei's dedication to innovations in the face of challenges posed by the ban. Huawei's swift response to the ban, which includes the creation of Harmony OS aligns with the call, for profound transformations advocated by a perspective of rejuvenation. Huawei's actions indicate an endeavor to avoid being trapped in improvements and instead embrace transformative innovation as a means to navigate through the ban successfully.

Strategic Improvement Perspective (Exploitation Strategy): Huawei's emphasis on the market and exploration of strategies is in line with their perspective of strategic improvement. The company aims to outshine its competitors by providing innovative value propositions. Huawei has the difficulty of striking a balance between ground-breaking inventions and continual improvements. Huawei's prohibition has forced the company to improve its business strategy in order to stay competitive.

Management of the Paradox:

Huawei's approach, to addressing the paradox in their situation is through a strategy called "Balancing." According to the text Huawei carefully balanced their innovation efforts while also focusing on their core strengths. This involves managing both exploration (such as Harmony OS and App Gallery) and exploitation (including selling HONOR and enhancing existing products) strategies. The company aimed to navigate the challenges imposed by the ban by finding a ground, between exploring possibilities and leveraging their current capabilities.

Do I agree with the position taken by Huawei on the tension?

In summary, I agree with their way of handling the tension. Huawei has taken an adaptable approach, in response to the trade war and subsequent ban. Throughout this period Huawei has shown determination calculated decision making and faced hurdles. Despite a decline in their smartphone business they have managed to maintain a presence in the Chinese market. In an effort to reduce reliance on ecosystems Huawei has developed Harmony OS. Made investments in App Gallery. However ongoing US regulations and decreasing consumer confidence worldwide pose challenges. The ability of Huawei to innovate navigate environments effectively and potentially form strategic alliances will determine its future

success. By navigating this situation Huawei has demonstrated resilience and strategic adaptability.

7.3 Reflections on performance and advice related to SDG – 9, 8 and 12

Huawei's position and strategies, as outlined in the evaluation, align with several aspects of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG). Let's reflect on Huawei's performance and provide advice related to SDG goals:

Reflections on SDG 9 and SDG 8

Technological Innovation (SDG 9):

- **Positive Aspects:** Huawei's approach, to exploration, which involves the creation of Harmony OS demonstrates their dedication to advancement. This corresponds with SDG 9. Contributes, to the establishment of infrastructure the promotion of inclusive and sustainable industrialization and the fostering of innovation.
- **Challenges:** The trade disagreement and the limitations imposed have influenced Huawei's innovation. It's crucial for them to find a way to strike a balance, between exploring opportunities and leveraging their strengths in order to overcome these challenges and maintain a competitive edge, in the market.

Economic Growth and Employment (SDG 8);

- **Positive Aspects:** Huawei's strategic approach, which includes selling its brand HONOR showcases their dedication to sustaining growth. They prioritize their business. Strive to enhance their products thus contributing to the attainment of Development Goal 8 by promoting term and inclusive economic progress.
- **Challenges:** The trade limitations have indeed affected Huawei's smartphone business. It is of importance for them to adeptly maneuver through this challenge all the while keeping their attention, on growth and employment in order to attain long term success.

Here are some suggestions, for achieving SDG 12 which focuses on Consumption and Production;

- **Improve Transparency and Ethical Sourcing;** It is of importance to improve the transparency of our supply chain so that we can ensure the sourcing of materials. We must effectively communicate these endeavors to consumers allowing them to fully appreciate Huawei's dedication to consumption and production.
- **Support Green Technology;** We should keep investing in research and development, for energy devices, packaging and innovative solutions that help minimize the impact of Huawei's products.
- **Foster Stakeholder Collaboration;** Work together with experts, from industries, government bodies and non governmental organizations to develop guidelines, for the management of consumption and production practices.

8 Tension 4

8.1 Identification and description of Huawei's position on the tension

Compliance vs. Choice

Over the last few years, Huawei has chosen to break industry rules, facing several compliance breaches in the past, ranging from engaging in unfair trade practices, such as price dumping, to bribing government officials to win contracts (Williams & Dilanian, 2019a; Yap et al., 2019a). Making it hard to believe that they could adhere to regulations at all at some point. Still, the concept of compliance has a lot of different subcategories that can be analysed. This report section will focus on their stand within the industry context and, more specifically, their stand on data privacy and security.

Huawei has had multiple compliance concerns with privacy regulations, particularly General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance. In 2018 Huawei has therefore formed a Global Cyber Security and User Privacy Protection Committee (GSPC) with that they wanted to guarantee that privacy regulations are effectively implemented (Huawei Privacy Protection, 2018a). Also, complying to the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that came into force on May 25 in 2018 (Proton Technologies AG, 2018a). Still, Huawei has been accused of storing and collecting personal data without the permission or consent of their users and using this data for unauthorized purposes (CBC News, 2019; The New York Times, 2019).

In 2020 Gaia X was created a European initiative with the main goal of building a secure and trustworthy data infrastructure for industrial cooperation in all sectors (Sanyal & Shankar, 2020). The consortium, which includes representatives from European businesses, research, and government, aims to strengthen privacy and security with new standards and certifications (Gaia-X, n.d.). Key players, from America and China that are participating in this initiative, are Google Cloud, Amazon Web Services, Alibaba Cloud, and als Huawei.

Since 2020, Huawei has been one of the members of the GAIA-X consotium. Foreign companies, which also includes Huawei, are the at the current state the minority in the consortium. However, they will be able to apply for certification in compliance with the rules by relying on European players (BMWK, n.d.). Furthermore, Huawei has actively participated in prototype activities that adhere to the standards of the International Data Space

Association (IDSA) and GAIA-X (O'Brien et al., 2022). These prototypes use real-world situations from the supply chain ecosystem, with an emphasis on the bidirectional flow of sensitive production data and documentation. This demonstrates Huawei's dedication to remaining current on developing standards and frameworks.

Huawei is studying applications for federated trustworthy AI, such as wind power plant management and maintenance, to strike a balance between compliance and allowing new AI capabilities. The technique entails integrating AI with physical equipment in order to solve concerns about sharing sensitive operational data.

8.2 Evaluation of the position taken by Huawei

Compliance:

On the one hand Huawei is adhering to standards that are specified by the Gaia-X since complying with them is highly important for participating in the EU digital landscape. Furthermore, it is regulatory intended that the members of the consortium align their operations to the ones proposed by Gaia X. Thirdly, the whole initiative is based on Data Governance Models and every must comply to show that they are committed to security and transparency in their practices.

Choice:

Huawei get the opportunity to actively shape and contribute to innovative data services participation in developing the landscape further. Since Gaia X is a collaborative ecosystem Huawei is able to position itself as a leader by incorporating the knowledge that is being provided by the consortium. International Data Spaces Association is one of the driving forces behind the Gaia X project – their goal is to have a diverse and competitive environment in the data market. Huawei's choice of complying to that puts them into the the red ocean but also secures their survival in a sense making them more durable.

Huawei's position on the tension:

According to the facts presented, at the current state Huawei seems to favour compliance above choice towards the outside perspective, particularly in terms of data governance, privacy, and standards alignment. And here it needs to be distinguished what favours means.

It is meant in a way that strategically adheres to the environment of the EU market. Huawei is actively involved in initiatives that follow multiple International and European standards, for example those that were established by GAIA-X and the International Data Space Association (IDSA). The focus on main pillars as data sovereignty, trust infrastructure, and compliance with legislation such as GDPR demonstrates a dedication of Huawei to following established guidelines and procedures.

While Huawei is also choosing to work on breakthrough initiatives such federated trustworthy AI (O'Brian et al., 2022), it focuses on assuring compliance with data protection legislation and industry standards. The emphasis on privacy by design, control over sensitive data, and adherence to legislation indicates at least from the outside perspective a desire for a compliant and controlled approach. It is important to remember that the strategic decisions between compliance and in choice may not be fully incompatible in general (based on the topic of data privacy), and Huawei may be attempting to achieve a compromise by balancing the two. However, based on the information provided, the corporation seems to put a high value on compliance as a guiding concept in its data projects, for now.

Do I agree with the position taken by Huawei on the tension?

Agreeing with its current way of handling because at the moment they do not really have another option. Being viewed so critically and trying to keep up with the competition. They need to build up their image as being trustworthy again, especially in the EU and American markets. Only after rebuilding the trust of the costumers and governments they can opt to go more in the direction of choice.

Industry Dynamics Perspective:

They have to adopt to certain market requirements in order to stay competitive. It is highly demanded by the context; other big players influence the company strongly in adopting and adhering to the standards of the EU. Since Huawei is one of many of its kind in a red ocean (book) the competitors and also the demands of the consumers are highly influential. They are active in over 170 countries making it impossible to ignore regional market requirements. In this they do not necessarily have to take the leadership role (especially in the EU market).

Being adaptive to the market trends and also benefitting from the collaboration within the ecosystem of Gaia X they are not taking the lead but rather staying in the wind shadow of their competitors potentially benefiting more in this position. When Huawei would go against the EU set rules and regulations it would miss out on the market opportunities. Even when the company might not fully stand behind the actions on a value-based view it certainly provides benefits to the stakeholders at this point, at least inside the EU markets.

Industry Leadership Perspective:

On the other hand, Huawei contributes to set a high quality of industry practices setting a cornerstone for other companies in this field and being a role model for other companies. Being part of initiatives like Gaia X or joining in federated AI practices displays a visionary approach and helping shape the industry.

8.3 Reflections on performance and advice related to SDG – 9, 8 and 12

Looking at the project of Gaia X it helps Huawei can indirectly contribute to the SDGs. Here is why:

SDG 8 Focus of Decent Work and Economic Growth

- **Challenge:** While Huawei's adoption of IDSA ideas promotes bidirectional data interchange for economic development, the sustainability of these practices remains a challenge. Ensuring long-term, inclusive development requires continuous efforts and vigilance.
- **Positive Aspect:** Huawei's adoption of IDSA ideas for bidirectional data interchange in a supply-chain ecosystem can contribute to innovation-driven job opportunities. By supporting the integration of digital technology Huawei plays a role in the creation of new employment opportunities.

SDG 9 Focus of Innovation and Infrastructure

- **Challenge:** Despite positive strides in networked manufacturing within the GAIA-X project, the challenge lies in ensuring sustainable industrialization and innovation. Huawei's commitment to robust infrastructure needs to be consistently aligned with environmental and social sustainability goals.

- **Positive Aspect:** Huawei's involvement in the GAIA-X project, especially in co-funding a project focusing on networked manufacturing, demonstrates a commitment to robust infrastructure and innovation. The interconnected approach, spanning factories, third-party ISVs, and cloud services, signifies positive strides in building resilient and innovative industrial processes.

SDG 12 Focus of Responsible Consumption and Production

- **Challenge:** While Huawei's efforts in federated trustworthy AI align with responsible consumption and production, the challenge lies in ensuring these actions lead to long-term positive impact. Sustainable practices, especially in data management and AI, must be continuously prioritized.
- **Positive Aspect:** Huawei Cloud's exploration of federated trustworthy AI aligns with SDG 12 by promoting ethical AI practices. The effort to ensure AI reliability across industry sectors, such as predictive maintenance and demand-supply matchmaking, reflects a commitment to responsible technology development. By addressing concerns about sensitive data exchange, Huawei contributes to promoting sustainable consumption and production.

9 Discussion

Huawei's strategic choices, as demonstrated by the example of the Mate 9 smartphone indicate a consideration of responsible behavior. This goes along, with De Wits (2004) assertion that such actions often come with costs. The company seems to prioritize factors over a commitment to social causes, which is a common challenge for organizations trying to balance financial constraints and ethical obligations. The existing literature establishes a connection between Huawei's position and the theoretical foundations of collaboration strategies within the same industry (Kock et al., n.d.). Collaboration, as emphasized by Inayat and Hamid (2013) requires finding the balance, between competition and cooperation while focusing on defined objectives and effective communication. The alignment observed between Huawei's actions and the literature indicates a coherence that can contribute to the success of strategies.

Analyzing Huawei's network level strategy as highlighted by Huang (2019) provides evidence, for the importance of partnerships in gaining an advantage. This aligns with the findings of Lendel et al. (2015). Vodak et al. (2014) who emphasize the significance of objectives and effective communication for successful cooperation strategies. Quoting Huawei's CEO as referenced by Huang (2019) establishes a connection to these aspects reinforcing the need for clarity and efficient communication in endeavors. The literature review offers context for understanding Huawei's approach linking insights obtained from studying strategy processes, strategic innovation and the balance between exploitation and exploration. Wit (2020) highlights the importance of timing, methodologies and stakeholder involvement in strategy development aligning with Huawei's actions. Strategic innovation, discussed by Schlegelmilch et al. (2003) Kataria (2013) and Anderson and Markides (2006) echoes Huawei's efforts in innovations such as Harmony OS and AppGallery. The company's focus on learning processes, leadership and an entrepreneurial mindset corresponds with existing literature, on innovation.

Huawei's approach of selling HONOR as a way to exploit opportunities and simultaneously developing Harmony OS to explore technologies reflects the paradox, between exploiting established practices and exploring approaches as discussed by Piruncharoen et al. (2011). By using the framework presented in the literature review, which includes aspects such as

strategy formulation, innovation and the balance between exploitation and exploration we can analyze Huawei's actions comprehensively. The company's responses, to the ban indicate an understanding of management concepts discussed in prior research.

10 Conclusion

To summarize the main objective of this study was to provide an analysis of Huawei's corporate approach focusing on key aspects discussed in the book "Strategy, in an International Perspective" by Bob de Wit and Ron Meyer. The primary goals of the study were to explore Huawei's business strategies, as well as understand how the organization handles conflicts within four strategic dimensions; strategy, strategy content, strategy process and strategy context.

The research findings provide insights, into the decisions made by Huawei across dimensions. Huawei, being a leader in ICT has shown adaptability and dynamism in response to challenges like the trade war and subsequent bans. The company has effectively managed the balance between exploring possibilities and maximizing existing resources through rejuvenation and strategic improvement perspectives. Huawei's commitment to innovation is evident through initiatives like expanding market presence with Harmony OS focusing on enhancing their product lineup and introducing the HONOR sub brand. In order to succeed in the smartphone industry it is essential to strike a balance, between capitalizing on opportunities and exploring avenues. Analyzing Huawei's situation brings attention to the intricacies involved in overcoming challenges while maintaining long term sustainability by balancing exploration and exploitation strategies.

Moreover the study examined how Huawei incorporates SDGs 1, 8, 9 and 12 in their initiatives. The reflective assessment uncovered that Huawei's strategic decisions contribute to growth development of infrastructure, promotion of innovation and responsible production of data spaces. This aligns, with the company's dedication to sustainable business practices showcasing its commitment to making a global impact. The conclusion further highlights that Huawei strategically prioritizes compliance in data governance, privacy protection and alignment with standards. Balancing compliance with innovation is effectively managed by being adaptable and recognizing the importance of adhering to EU standards for market opportunities. The company's actions such as participation in initiatives like GAIA X underscore its pledge, towards data sovereignty, trust based infrastructure and adherence to legislation.

Based on the conclusion the research has effectively achieved its goals by providing an analysis and evaluation of Huawei's business strategies. The insights gained contribute to an understanding of Huawei's decisions, their impact, and the company's approach to managing conflicts. The study emphasizes the significance of Huawei's agility, commitment to standards, and sustainability, as factors shaping the development of the ICT sector.

11 Recommendation

Research and Development: Since the Mate 9 of Huawei is ranked in the top 3 of most emitting radiation phones in 2018, one important recommendation for Huawei could be to invest in research and development. Research and development could help the organization get to know how they can reduce the radiation emitting properly. When Huawei knows how they could reduce the radiation, it would spare human health complaints as earlier mentioned in chapter 5.

Prioritizing employee's health and safety: Employees are the heart of every company. As earlier mentioned in chapter 5, employees of Huawei could cause health problems because of the producing process of making the Huawei Mate 9 device. The radiation is so really bad for humans' health, not only for those who buy the Huawei Mate 9, but also for the employees who have to create the device. One important recommendation for Huawei should be to take into account the health of their employees. Besides the fact that they first should tackle the amount of radiation which is in the Huawei Mate 9, they also should improve the circumstances for the employees, so they never have to work uncovered in an unprotected area as before. If the working conditions are good and safe, the health of their employees can be Safed. Think of offering protective working clothes for the employees who are working with processing devices and ventilation systems within the working area for some fresh air.

Stakeholders' engagement: To make it up to customers who purchased the Huawei Mate 9 device and experience demonstrable complaints, Huawei could offer compensation. Compensation in the form of a personal apology for the health problems they suffered from purchasing this device and a credit voucher with which they can purchase a better Huawei device in the future that contains less or no radiation.

Huawei's Fully Domestic Turnkey Solution: Huawei can enable the trust of the other firms in the industry to use this by offering them a full turnkey solution package for the domestic phone market. They can offer Harmony OS for free plus their brand new Kirin microprocessor chips which is a chip that was created despite the harsh sanctions to imposed on Huawei which aimed to keep their microchip production 8-10 years behind the rest of the competition. These new chips are only now 7nm in size making them only 4-5 years behind current phone technology employed by their Global Competition's 3nm as of 2023. The chips can also be

offered a discounted rate as they are domestically produced, and in addition to HMS Core (Huawei ID). It is a safer bet for firms in China to employ this into their own phones as the fear of getting hit by sanctions themselves is an all too real possibility for them. This is especially true as the 2024 United States presidential elections commences, a new president who might have hostile policies to China might assume Presidency.

Strategic Partnerships and Alliances: In light of the complex geopolitical landscape, Huawei ought to actively look for strategic alliances and collaborations with businesses that share its objectives. Partnerships can offer chances for reciprocal development and assist in resolving some legal and commercial obstacles. Building solid connections with other IT companies will help Huawei's ecosystem and market share.

Global Communication and Transparency: To alleviate the concerns and doubts over its commercial activities, Huawei should enhance its global communication plan. Building confidence among international stakeholders is facilitated by establishing transparency on its strategy, security procedures, and adherence to regulations. If Huawei wants to maintain and increase its market share worldwide, it must effectively communicate.

Deepen Engagement in Associations: Emphasise the continuation of the compliance with industry standards, especially in the EU market space. The initiatives Gaia X and International Data Space Association will help Huawei to regain the trust of their stakeholders and rebuild their image (especially their customers and the investors within the EU). The other benefit of actively engaging in the Gaia X is the exchange and the access to information within the industry which could help them significantly to keep up to date with industry practices.

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